

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Nichols****FIRST NAME: Maita****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with the page number in-text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2009, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2009, 5 -12)
3. Personal v Academic (EUCLID 2009, 12)
4. Rules of Thumb (EUCLID 2009, 14)
5. What is a Style Guide and why would I need one (EUCLID 2009, 24)
6. American v British English (EUCLID 2009, 27-34)
7. Latin abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2009, 56-59)

THE ART OF ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As a visual learner, I found that the online video helped me tremendously while installing Grammarly and Zotero because I do not have a penchant for computers or technology. I was also used to the Harvard referencing system, so learning about Turabian has been a completely new experience. This essay is a brief exploration of the seven concepts I found to be the most interesting and useful. Through studying these areas, I hope to have a better understanding of EUCLID's essay writing requirements.

2) STARTING AN ESSAY

As a teacher, I find it highly annoying when students approach me to check on their work just before the deadline. Therefore I agree with the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack when it states that "You can't write a successful essay unless you give yourself time..." (EUCLID 2009, 6). Or in the words of a rather delightful Malay proverb, "Prepare the umbrella before it rains"(Awaken The Greatness Within 2021). When writing an essay is left until the last minute, it is a rushed process, and this

subsequently results in the author making mistakes that could be avoided with another read through.

The next piece of guidance the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack states is that the student should “Define the question and Analyse the task” (EUCLID 2009, 6). The University of Leeds expands upon this statement by explaining that “Most formal academic writing at university is set by and written for, an academic tutor or assessor, and there should be clear criteria against which they will mark your work” (University of Leeds 2012, section 2). There are specific criteria (EUCLID LMS 2019) on which this essay is marked. This period aims for the student to identify and implement the appropriate language, structure, and writing style for academic papers at Euclid University. The rationale behind these learning aims is that an institution must have a sense of cohesion with all its documentation.

The final piece of advice given in the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack on starting an essay is to have a plan. Similarly, as it would be foolish to go on a new journey without a map (or Satnav), it is essential to write a plan before writing an essay. Without a plan, one might easily wander off-topic, make repetitions or fail to answer the assigned question completely.

3) PLAGIARISM

The ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack defines plagiarism as “... when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2009, 10). In other words, plagiarism is stealing someone else's words and ideas and passing them off as our own. The chapter further explains that quoting other people is fine as long as it is acknowledged through the correct use of citations.

The concept of plagiarism and the development of technology go hand in hand. Linda Adler-Kassner, Chris M. Anson and Rebecca Moore Howard quote an article from 1910 which states, “The boys and girls of the land are learning . . . lessons in wrongdoing” (Framing Plagiarism, 2008) concerning the advent of moving pictures. The arrival of the internet and the explosion of different sources onto our screens has ensured that “There is no doubt that student plagiarism can now be considered a widespread, and perhaps systemic, problem (Roberts 2007, 47).

Given the proliferation of plagiarism, it comes as no surprise that academic institutions are very keen to identify and severely punish any student caught misappropriating another scholar's work. As a psychologist, I was particularly interested in Amy Roubillard's article called *Pass It On: Revising The Plagiarism is Theft Metaphore* (2009). Roubillard suggests that we might disregard associating plagiarism with theft and reframe the emphasis onto the original author deserving credit for their idea. She explains that this approach removes the somewhat binary implication that students are by nature criminals and lazy because their predilection is towards stealing and that teachers are police and judges who want to punish lawbreakers. As a teacher, I

will absorb this new way of thinking about plagiarism because it feels much less punitive, more positive and much more respectful of both students and teachers.

4) PERSONAL VS ACADEMIC STYLE

In the ACA-40D1 period one (1) coursepack, there is a very brief section about the difference between personal and academic writing styles. The PDF advises that Academic writing abandons the use of contractions and that authors should take care to employ a variety of connectors that will ensure a sense of logical flow. The PDF also warns against a robotic writing style, leaving the reader without understanding the author's personality. As a psychologist, I was very struck by the different writing and presentation styles of the authors who co-wrote the coursepack. The first and foremost section followed the academic style but was dotted with humour and had an expansive feeling tone. Whereas the crib sheet was very concise, there was no use of humour, and the author employed tables to convey information. Whilst I appreciate that a crib sheet by its nature suggests a condensed format, I am very tempted to suggest that that first section of the course pack may have been written by authors with an extroverted temperament, and the crib sheet has been compiled by someone who is an introvert. I might also suggest that maybe the first section was written by at least one author who is a social scientist and maybe more at ease with qualitative data whereas, the second section was compiled by someone who works mainly with quantitative data (which might explain the preference for using tables).

5) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

Chapter three (14-16) of the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack provides the student with some basic rules about writing essays. It explains that it is necessary to state the thesis at the beginning and to do it simply. The thesis is an essential component of essay writing because without one, it is impossible to follow the second guideline, which is to "Stay Focused" (EUCLID 2009, 14). This essay is titled "The Art of Essay Writing", and as such, one would expect it to explore the issue of writing a good essay. Going off-topic might include writing a paragraph about how to make paper. Paper is a vital component of the whole essay writing process, but knowing how to make paper will not help me write a better essay.

The next rule is to avoid using sweeping claims to start a paragraph. This is because they are often inaccurate, and they also suggest that the author has not adequately thought about what they are writing. The rule which follows this "Write Clearly" (EUCLID 2009, 14) also refers to the author being precise and accurate with their use of words. The basic rule is that simplicity is best. The following rule, "Don't make writing boring or clumsy" (EUCLID 2009, 15), refers back to the idea that good writing contains a good flow. Reading the text out loud generally helps to ensure that the essay sounds right and fits together logically.

It is also essential that any claims made in an essay are supplemented with evidence. This is essential because in an academic essay, others who read it want to follow the author's process. If I make the statement that "essay writing is a logical process that makes sense", I would follow this statement by giving examples from other sources that agree that essay writing is a logical process that makes sense. This helps to prove the validity of my statement.

The final rule is to respect the content of the work on the reading list despite any initial reservations one may have. I believe that context is our friend in helping us to avoid sounding arrogant. For example, I might write "that before Galileo, common people held the ridiculous view that the Earth was the centre of the universe". To express that this view is ridiculous does not acknowledge the context of this belief. The Greek philosopher Aristotle believed that the Earth was the centre of the universe because it did not move, unlike the rest of the planets. Until relatively recently in humanity's history, knowledge was only available to the upper echelons of society who were able to read. Life was very hard for peasants who lived in poverty and had very little time contemplating the universe. Therefore, if you lived in a world where the literate few told you that the Earth was the centre of the universe, you had no reason to doubt them.

6) **TURABIAN STYLE**

As previously mentioned in this essay, a common writing style is essential to maintaining a sense of cohesion in all documents written by students at EUCLID University. Our university prescribes that students must write using the Turabian style which was originally developed from a practical need.

The webpage <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/turabian/about/history.html> describes how Mary Turabian began life as a university secretary who later became a dissertation secretary. In this latter role, she noticed that students would benefit from essay writing advice. She responded by publishing a small pamphlet (1955) containing some advice for writing academic papers in the Chicago style. In its later editions, the small pamphlet expanded into a detailed textbook containing a wide selection of information ranging from how to develop thesis ideas to citing websites and television programmes correctly. Whilst being a handy essay writing tool, it is incredibly dense, and it left me feeling a little overwhelmed. However, Turabian herself gives some excellent advice to writers in this situation. She writes, "The bad news is that there's no sure way to avoid such moments. The good news is that most of us have them, and they usually pass" (Turabin 2013, 48). This wise and timeless advice feels applicable to most stressful or unhappy life situations.

There was one inconsistency in the APA-401D period one (1) coursepack, which states "that when you cite something in the text of your paper, you simply need only to put the author's name in parenthesis with the page number that the information came from" (EUCLID 2009, 6). Whereas elsewhere in the coursepack, it states that "In-text [citations]: (EUCLID 2019, page no.)" in other words, the year, the author and page

number need to be included. The example response paper (Gu 2020) also consists of the year as well the author and page numbers for in-text citations.

7) AMERICAN VS UK ENGLISH

As a British person, I found the section on American Vs UK English (EUCLID 2009, 27) in the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack exciting. Although I have chosen to write this essay in UK English, it is with a heavy heart that I must concede that America, as a global superpower, has a much more considerable influence on the world's stage than the UK. The article "Goodbye Britannia" (Oliver 2016) explains that Brexit was initially a ploy to keep the British Conservative party in power against the growing opposition of the right-wing, anti-European United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP). However, very little thought was given to how this might affect Britain's economic standing and political influence throughout the rest of the world. It, therefore, seems quite likely that America's dominance over the UK will remain for the foreseeable future.

It was also fascinating to read about the differences in sentence structure; for example, American English using "Math" instead of "Maths" (Euclid 2009, 28). Having studied theatre and drama, I have read and performed both English and American scripts, and most playwrights will write in the character's dialect. One line spoken by a character called Florence in the play "N" written by Adrienne Pender (2017) is a fantastic example of African American English:

FLORENCE: Ain't heard'a him before.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

My exposure to Latin has been limited to regular church attendance as a child, studying Analytical Psychology and everyday Latin abbreviations.

The Reuters article "Facts on Latin in the Roman Catholic Church" (2011) explains how Jesus spoke Aramaic, which is similar to Hebrew. The Gospels were written in Greek, and later, St. Jerome wrote the Vulgate Bible, which translated Greek into Latin. In 1969 Pope Paul VI modernised mass, and the changes included allowing services to be celebrated in each country's mother tongue. However, the Latin mass still remains popular among worshippers who prefer the beauty of the old language, and there are still Latin words and phrases incorporated into contemporary mass.

Latin as a means of describing the spiritual also connects to CG Jung's use of alchemy to describe the soul's progression along the individuation journey. There are four stages of the alchemical journey which are;

1. Nigredo – The Unconscious, the Shadow, the depression which brings people to psychoanalysis

2. Albedo- The separation and identification of unconscious complexes
3. Rubedo- The passion which comes from a new way of being
4. Conjunctio – The integration of conscious and unconscious processes.

On a mundane level, I was amazed by the number of Latin words that are part of everyday language. As I looked through the table of Latin Abbreviations (EUCLID 2009, 56-61) in the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack, there were several words whose origin surprised me. Ad hoc, Ad lib, caveat, de jure and status quo are phrases that I now are Latin.

9) CONCLUSION

Writing this essay has given me a deeper appreciation for the level of attention to detail required whilst composing an academic paper. It has also given me even more respect for students who do not have English as their first language. I have also learned that the Turabian writing style is both comprehensive and nuanced. The textbook is filled with instructions for every conceivable essay writing area, from gathering ideas to proofreading drafts. By the end of this section of the PhD, I hope that I will feel much more confident about applying it correctly to my work.

I have enjoyed learning about a new way of thinking about plagiarism, pondering the psychological implications of different individuals' writing styles and the context behind American English's prevalence over UK English. As this course continues, I look forward to increasing my knowledge of the Turabian writing style even more.

REFERENCES

- Adler-Kassner, Linda, Chris M. Anson, and Rebecca Moore Howard. 2008. 'Framing Plagiarism'. In *Originality, Imitation, and Plagiarism*, edited by Caroline Eisner and Martha Vicinus, 231–46. Teaching Writing in the Digital Age. University of Michigan Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv65sxxk1.23>.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period I*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.
- 'Kate L. Turabian, A Manual for Writers, Eighth Edition'. n.d. Kate L. Turabian, A Manual for Writers, Eighth Edition. Accessed 2 April 2021. <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/turabian.html>.
- Library. n.d. 'Academic Writing'. Accessed 24 March 2021. https://library.leeds.ac.uk/info/14011/writing/106/academic_writing/2.
- Meah, Asad. 2018. '35 Inspirational Quotes On Preparation | AwakenTheGreatnessWithin'. 1 April 2018. <https://www.awakenthegreatnesswithin.com/35-inspirational-quotes-on-preparation/>.
- 'N - A Full-Length Drama African American History Play & The N Word'. n.d. *Havescripts Blue Moon Plays* (blog). Accessed 3 April 2021. <https://havescripts.com/product/n-play-adrienne-pender/>.
- OLIVER, TIM. 2016. 'GOODBYE BRITANNIA? THE INTERNATIONAL IMPLICATIONS OF BRITAIN'S VOTE TO LEAVE THE EU'. *Geopolitics, History, and International Relations* 8, no. 2: 214–33. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26805970>.
- Roberts, Tim S. 2007. 'Student Plagiarism and the Internet'. *Educational Technology* 47, no. 2: 45–47. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44429488>.
- Robillard, Amy. 2009. 'Pass It On: Revising the "Plagiarism Is Theft" Metaphor'. *JAC* 29, no. 1/2: 405–35. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20866905>.
- Staff, Reuters. 2011. 'Facts on Latin in the Roman Catholic Church'. *Reuters*, 13 May 2011. <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-pope-latin-facts-idUSTRE74C2C220110513>.
- Turabian, Kate. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.